

STUDENTS' ACQUISITION OF BASIC SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS THROUGH THE 9E LEARNING CYCLE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effectiveness of the 9E Learning Cycle in enhancing the Basic Science Process Skills (BSPS) of Grade 8 students in Physics at Pangantucan National High School during the first quarter of School Year 2024–2025. Specifically, the study examined students' skills in observing, classifying, measuring, predicting, inferring, and communicating. A quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design was employed involving eighty-four (84) students divided into two intact groups: the experimental group exposed to the 9E Learning Cycle and the control group exposed to a non-9E instructional approach. Data were gathered using an adapted Rubric of Science Process Skills and analyzed using descriptive statistics and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Findings revealed that both groups improved after the intervention; however, the 9E group demonstrated higher levels of BSPS across all indicators. The experimental group achieved a High Level in overall BSPS, while the control group achieved only a Medium Level. ANCOVA results further revealed a statistically significant difference between the two groups in favor of the 9E Learning Cycle. The findings suggest that the 9E Learning Cycle is an effective inquiry-based instructional model for improving students' Basic Science Process Skills in Physics.

Keywords: *9E Learning Cycle, Basic Science Process Skills*

INTRODUCTION

Physics is often regarded as one of the most difficult science subjects because students are required to understand abstract concepts, apply mathematical relationships, and analyze scientific phenomena that cannot always be directly observed (Camarao & Nava, 2017; Wangchuk et al., 2023). In science education, the development of Basic Science Process Skills (BSPS), such as observing, classifying, measuring, predicting, inferring, and communicating, is essential in helping learners investigate and understand scientific concepts. These skills also contribute to the development of scientific literacy and critical thinking (Gizaw & Sota, 2023). However, studies revealed that many students still demonstrate low proficiency in science process skills due to the continued use of teacher-centered instruction, which limits opportunities for inquiry, exploration, and hands-on learning activities (Aglosolos, 2020; Salmeron, 2023).

To address this concern, inquiry-based instructional models have been widely promoted in science education. One of these models is the 9E Learning Cycle developed by Kaur and Gakhar (2014), which consists of the phases Elicit, Engage, Explore, Explain, Echo, Elaborate, Evaluate, Emend, and E-search. The 9E Learning Cycle is grounded in constructivist learning principles, which emphasize that learners actively construct knowledge through meaningful experiences and interactions (Piaget, 1976). Previous studies have shown that the 9E Learning Cycle improves science process skills and conceptual understanding among students (Putri et al., 2021; Alfian et al., 2024).

Despite the potential of the 9E Learning Cycle, studies examining its effectiveness in improving Basic Science Process Skills in Physics within the local context remain limited. Thus, this study was conducted to determine the effectiveness of the 9E Learning Cycle in enhancing the Basic Science Process Skills of Grade 8 students at Pangantucan National High School during the first quarter of School Year 2024–2025.

Research Questions:

This study examined the Students' Basic Science Process Skills (BSPS) through the 9E Learning Cycle in Grade 8 science of Pangantucan National High School, Poblacion, Pangantucan, Bukidnon.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of students' acquisition of basic science process skills before and after their exposure to a 9E learning cycle and those in a non-9E learning cycle in terms of:
 - a. observing,
 - b. classifying,
 - c. measuring,
 - d. predicting,
 - e. inferring, and
 - f. communicating?

2. Is there a significant difference in the learners' acquisition of basic science process skills before and after their exposure to the 9E learning cycle and those in a non-9E learning cycle?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design to determine the effectiveness of the 9E learning cycle in the acquisition of basic science process skills among Grade 8 students at Pangantucan National High School, Poblacion, Pangantucan, Bukidnon, during the first quarter of the School Year 2024–2025. Two intact heterogeneous sections were selected randomly, with one section assigned to the experimental group, exposed to the 9E learning cycle, and the other to the control group, exposed to the non-9E learning cycle. A pretest and posttest were administered to determine the students' level of BSPS and the significant difference when exposed to the 9E learning cycle and to the non-9E learning cycle.

The study used a Rubric of Science Process Skills adapted from Bahtiar and Dukomalamo (2019), Halim et al. (2021), and Utami et al. (2013). The rubric covered six (6) basic science process skills, namely: observing, classifying, measuring, predicting, communicating, and inferring. Each skill was measured using specific indicators: classifying consisted of four (4) indicators; observing, measuring, predicting, and communicating each consisted of three (3) indicators; and inferring consisted of two (2) indicators. To ensure the validity of the instrument, it underwent content validation by three (3) experts in science education. Furthermore, to minimize scoring bias, four (4) inter-raters evaluated the students' performance using the rubric. The mean score from the inter-raters was computed and converted into a percentage score using the formula adapted from Chabalengula (2012):

$$\text{Science Process (\%)} = \frac{\text{Score Obtained}}{\text{Score Max}} \times 100$$

The computed percentage scores were then interpreted using the Category of Percentage Ranges of Students' Science Process Skills, adapted from Arikunto (2013):

Rating	Range of Percentage	Qualitative Interpretation
3	76% - 100%	High
2	60 - 75%	Medium
1	<60%	Low

The quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to determine the students' level of BSPS. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to determine any significant differences in students' BSPS between students exposed to the 9E learning cycle and those exposed to the non-9E learning cycle.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Students' Level of Basic Science Process Skills in pretest and posttest for 9E and non-9E groups

Basic Science Process Skills	9E				NON-9E			
	PRETEST		POSTTEST		PRETEST		POSTTEST	
	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI	MEAN	QI
Observing	59.70	LL	87.86	HL	57.35	LL	81.30	HL
Predicting	51.16	LL	84.11	HL	55.29	LL	75.20	ML
Classifying	48.25	LL	79.65	HL	44.71	LL	72.16	ML
Communicating	41.34	LL	78.04	HL	39.02	LL	76.15	HL
Measuring	58.92	LL	75.19	ML	60.97	ML	72.35	ML
Inferring	42.25	LL	72.27	ML	39.02	LL	71.95	ML
Overall Mean	50.27	LL	79.52	HL	49.39	LL	74.85	ML

Before the intervention, in terms of the observing skill, both groups obtained a “Low Level”, with the 9E group obtaining 59.70 and the non-9E group obtaining 57.35. It implies that students' observation skills are comparable before the intervention. After the intervention, both groups showed an improvement. The 9E group obtained a “High Level” with a mean score of 87.86, while the non-9E group also reached a “High Level” with a mean score of 81.30.

In the skill of classification, both groups were initially at a “Low Level” during the pretest, with the 9E group obtaining a mean score of 48.25 and the non-9E group obtaining a mean score of 44.71. It indicates that students had difficulty identifying similarities and differences among objects or phenomena and were not yet able to organize information systematically. After the intervention, the 9E group improved to a “High Level” with a mean score of 79.65, while the non-9E group reached only a “Medium Level” with a mean score of 72.16. It shows that the 9E Learning Cycle was more effective in developing students' classifying skills.

In the skill of measuring, during the pretest, the non-9E group obtained a slightly higher mean score (60.97) compared to the 9E group (58.92), although both were still at a “Low Level,” indicating limited accuracy and consistency in using measurement tools and recording quantitative data. After the intervention, the 9E group obtained a mean score of 75.19, and the non-9E group got 72.35, indicating an improvement to a “Medium Level”. Although both groups demonstrated progress, the 9E group slightly outperformed the non-9E group, indicating better development in the ability to use tools correctly and record more accurate measurements.

In terms of predicting, both groups obtained a “Low Level”, with the 9E group's mean score of 51.16 and the non-9E group's mean score of 55.29. Both groups have difficulty making scientifically supported forecasts before the intervention. After the intervention,

the 9E group improved to a “High Level” (84.11), while the non-9E group reached only a “Medium Level” (75.20), indicating that the 9E group performed better.

In the skill of inferring, both groups were initially at a “Low Level” during the pretest, with the 9E group obtaining a mean score of 42.25 and the non-9E group 39.02. It indicates that students had difficulty drawing logical conclusions from observed data and providing explanations supported by evidence. After the intervention, both groups improved to a “Medium Level,” with the 9E group obtaining a mean score of 72.27 and the non-9E group 71.95. Although the difference between the two groups is minimal, the results show that both instructional approaches helped students develop better ability in making inferences based on evidence. However, neither group reached a “High Level,” suggesting that inferring remains a challenging skill for students to fully master.

In the skill of communicating, both groups were initially at a “Low Level” during the pretest, with the 9E group obtaining a mean score of 41.34 and the non-9E group 39.02. It indicates that students had difficulty presenting their ideas clearly and organizing scientific information using appropriate formats such as tables, charts, or written explanations. Their ability to explain results and communicate findings was still limited at the beginning of the study. In the posttest, the results of both groups were very close, with the 9E group scoring 78.04 and the non-9E group scoring 76.15. Both reached a “High Level” of proficiency, showing that inquiry-based instruction, whether through the non-9E or 9E model, encouraged students to share their ideas, record data, and discuss scientific concepts. However, the slightly higher mean of the 9E group points to a more refined and accurate way of expressing scientific information.

The overall mean results show that both groups were initially at a “Low Level” during the pretest, with the 9E group obtaining a mean score of 50.27 and the non-9E group obtaining 49.39. It indicates that students in both groups started with limited proficiency in basic science process skills. After the intervention, both groups improved; however, the 9E group reached a “High Level” with a mean score of 79.52, while the non-9E group reached only a “Medium Level” with a mean score of 74.85. This result implies that although both the 9E and non-9E were effective in improving students’ basic science process skills, the 9E learning cycle was more effective in promoting higher levels of skill development.

The greater improvement in the 9E group implies that students were able to enhance a range of skills. This may be attributed to the additional phases of the 9E model, which provided more opportunities for reinforcement, feedback, and independent learning. The Echo phase allowed students to revisit and practice skills, the Emend phase supported improvement through feedback and reflection, and the E-search phase encouraged students to explore additional information and deepen their understanding.

The effectiveness of the 9E learning cycle can be explained through its alignment with constructivist learning, which emphasizes that learners actively construct knowledge through experience and reflection (Piaget, 1976). Similar findings were reported by Buwono et al. (2021) and Putri et al. (2021), who found that the structured and inquiry-

based nature of the 9E Learning Cycle contributed to improved science process skills and deeper conceptual understanding. This structured support may have contributed to the stronger development of higher-order skills observed in the 9E group.

Table 2. Analysis of Covariance (ANOVA) of Students' BSPS in the Posttest.

GROUP	N	MEAN	SD
9E Learning Cycle	43	3.63	.19
Non-9E Learning Cycle	41	3.08	.21
TOTAL	84	3.36	.34

Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Sig.
Group	6.539	1	6.359	154.232	.000*
Pre-test (Covariate)	.084	1	.084	2.027	.158
Error	3.339	81	.041		
Total	97.446	84			

Note: *-significant at the 0.05 level

The results revealed that the mean score of the 9E group is 3.63 (SD=.21) and the non-9E group had a mean score of 3.08 (SD=.19). The 9E group obtained a higher mean score as compared to the non-9E group. This implies that the students under exposed to the 9E learning cycle performed better than the students exposed to the non-9E. The result also indicates a significant difference between those exposed to the 9E learning cycle and those exposed to the non-9E learning cycle ($F = 154.232, p < 0.001$) in overall basic science process skills.

The findings suggest that the 9E Learning Cycle is an effective instructional model for improving students' BSPS. The higher performance of the 9E group may be attributed to the structured and inquiry-based nature of the model, which actively engages students in observation, questioning, exploration, reflection, and application of scientific concepts. Through repeated learning activities and opportunities for feedback and reflection, students may have developed a deeper understanding of scientific processes and improved confidence in performing science-related tasks.

These findings are consistent with the study of Alfian et al. (2024), which reported that the 9E Learning Cycle enhances a wide range of science process skills, from basic to more advanced competencies. Similarly, Putri (2021) found that the 9E Learning Cycle was more effective than the traditional approach in developing students' basic science process skills. According to Putri, the Echo, Emend, and E-search phases provide learners with opportunities for practice, feedback, reflection, and independent exploration, which are often limited in traditional classroom instruction. In the present study, these phases may have helped students refine their understanding, correct misconceptions,

and strengthen their science process skills. Furthermore, Laslo and Hartmann (2023) emphasized that technology-supported learning approaches that encourage exploration and collaboration promote deeper scientific thinking and scientific communication skills, which supports the present study's finding that the additional phases of the 9E Learning Cycle enhanced students' engagement and the development of science process skills.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn from the study:

1. Students exposed to the 9E learning cycle demonstrated greater improvement in observing, classifying, measuring, predicting, inferring, and communicating skills compared to those exposed to the non-9E learning cycle, indicating the effectiveness of the model in enhancing students' BSPS.
2. A significant difference existed between groups in relation to basic science process skills as exposed to the 9E learning cycle. The mean difference was in favor to the 9E learning cycle group. Thus, exposure to the 9E learning cycle successfully enhanced students' basic science process skills.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are hereby given:

1. Science teachers may integrate the 9E learning cycle into their science instruction to enhance students' basic science process skills. They may also provide additional learning activities that further strengthen students' measuring, inferring, and communicating skills, as these areas showed less improvement compared to other basic science process skills. Laboratory activities, collaborative tasks, and hands-on investigations may help improve these competencies.
2. Future researchers may conduct similar studies with a longer intervention period to determine whether prolonged exposure to the 9E learning cycle yields greater improvements in measuring, inferring, and communicating skills. Additionally, they may also explore the effectiveness of the 9E learning cycle in developing Integrated Science Process Skills (ISPS) specially among students in higher grade levels.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher observed ethical conduct throughout the study. An IERC clearance was secured from Central Mindanao University regarding the ethical considerations of the study. Then, the researcher also secured permission from the teachers and students. Collected information remained anonymous and was stored securely. Any potential conflicts of interest between the researchers and participants were addressed and disclosed.

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